

Cybernetics

Abstract: *Cybernetics is a science that studies the mechanisms of communication and control in systems, with an emphasis on circular, feedback, or self-referential processes. It is concerned not so much with the material or components of a system, but with the abstracted relations, functions, and information flows that govern its operation. It focuses on how systems use information in regulating their actions and steering towards their goal states, while counteracting perturbations. Being inherently transdisciplinary, cybernetic modelling can be applied to systems of any kind: physical, technological, biological, ecological, psychological, social, or any combination of those. Second-order cybernetics in particular studies the role of the (human) observer in the construction of models of systems and other observers. This self-referential modelling has direct applications to the study of social systems.*

Keywords: control, self-regulation, information, communication, second-order epistemology, Macy Conferences, circularity

Origin of the field

Cybernetics is a transdisciplinary science that emerged out of a series of conferences held between 1946 and 1953 by some forty prominent intellectuals, including Warren McCulloch (chair), Norbert Wiener, Gregory Bateson, Margaret Mead, Heinz von Foerster, John von Neumann, Claude Shannon and W. Ross Ashby. These meetings, initially on “Circular causal and feedback mechanisms in biological and social systems”, eventually became known as the Macy Conferences on Cybernetics. The participants sought to develop a conceptual foundation for an integration of the different scientific disciplines — most notably between the “hard” and the social sciences.

The threads tying these diverse approaches together were two newly developed notions: (1) Shannon’s theory of communication as the transmission of some abstract quantity called *information*; (2) the mechanism of *circular causality*, where information about the effect of some action is fed back to the system that performed it, thus allowing that system to correct any deviation between the effect it intended (goal) and the effect it actually perceives. This allowed cyberneticians to solve the old problem of how causal systems such as organisms can exhibit purpose or teleology (Rosenblueth, Wiener & Bigelow, 1943), namely by regulating their behavior so as to compensate for any perturbations that may push them away from their goals. These circular mechanisms of communication and control were expressed at such a level of abstraction that they could be used to model systems of any kind, including machines, organisms, human minds, and societies.

The name “cybernetics” was first used by the mathematician Norbert Wiener (1948) and proposed as a name for the field by von Foerster in 1949. Wiener’s English term “cybernetics” was borrowed from Ampère et. al. (1834) who coined the French “cybernétique” in their discussion of a scientific approach to civil government. The root of the notion, however, goes back to antiquity. The Greek κυβερνητικός (kybernetikos), meaning “(good at) steering”, was used by Plato and Aristotle in reference to the art of governing the state. The derived Latin words “gubernātor” and “gubernō” gave rise to the English words “governor” and “to govern”. The seminal work by Wiener (1948) revived the idea, applying it to machines and living organisms (only later jointly abstracted into “systems”), while providing a mathematical foundation for the study of the regulatory functions of information, communication, and feedback.

Themes of early cybernetics (1940’s - 1950’s)

The focus of the Macy Conferences was richly multidisciplinary. The experimental character and internal diversity of the early cybernetic movement can perhaps best be illustrated by a list of themes addressed in these conferences (Heims, 1991; Dupuy, 2000; American Society for Cybernetics, 2020):

- *Interdisciplinarity and metascience*: the need for a “meta-language” to go beyond the disciplinary lexicons;
- *Teleology and self-regulation*: purposive behaviour; mechanisms for self-regulation;
- *Perception and meaning*: “analog” and “digital” models of perception; distinction between meaning and information;
- *Communication and information*: the type of language necessary to analyse language itself; humour and paradox; communications in ants; small group dynamics;
- *Psychology, and psychiatry*: trauma; neurosis; language and symbols;

- *Neurophysiology and complexity*: complexity of the brain and of biological organisms;
- *Computation and formal modelling*: digital computers; simulated neural networks; automata; modelling of natural phenomena;
- *Observation*: the problem of the observer interfering with observed phenomena.

This compilation illustrates not only the eclecticism of cybernetics in the making, but also that the actual origins of the field were much more diffuse than may be suggested by later narratives. The unprecedented fusion of theories—contributed by engineers and anthropologists, biologists and sociologists, physicists and psychiatrists—generated much intellectual excitement. Nonetheless, the conferences did not result in a clear sense of accomplishment. McCulloch concluded "Our most notable agreement is that we have learned to know one another a bit better, and to fight fair in our shirt sleeves." Indeed, the conferences were marked by reportedly "brutal, intolerant" (Kline, 2015:199) mutual treatment between the representatives of the "hard" and the "soft" sides of the academic scene, exposing the deep differences in their perceptions and ways of reasoning.

Second-order cybernetics (1960's - 1980's)

While the problem of observation was explicitly addressed in just one of the Macy Conferences, it has been fuelling most controversy between the participants interested in systems architectures and modelling, and those interested in perception and meaning. The key differences between the two camps were formulated some twenty years later by Mead (1968) and von Foerster (1974), resulting in the retrospective grouping of cybernetic stances into *first-* and *second-order* ones. The split roughly followed the dividing line between the interest in engineered systems, on the one hand, and biological, psychological and social systems, on the other.

Second-order cybernetics, or "cybernetics of cybernetics" as it was initially called, concerned the application of cybernetic thinking *to itself*. Its main insight is that a cybernetician does not simply uncover the regulatory mechanisms inherent in the phenomenon of interest, but by the act of delineating a model introduces an additional control circuit. Quantum mechanics had already exposed the inevitable influence of the observer on the observed. Yet, this did not seem to apply to mechanical, macroscopic systems, such as machines. For engineered systems, the distinction between first-order and second-order seemed superfluous, because the regulatory circuits of an apparatus map straightforwardly to the model held by its designer. But for complex, "natural" systems, a model is always a simplified description, which ignores the aspects irrelevant to the purpose for which the model is constructed. Since the goal-directedness of systems is one of the central assumptions in cybernetic modelling, the fact that creating a model is in itself a goal-oriented, cognitive process complicated the issue. In the case of living organisms, this was further complicated by the cognitive activity performed by these organisms. For human minds and social systems, the most significant processes to be observed are largely composed of the cognitive activity performed by these systems. Therefore, the cognitive processes of the scientific observer constructing a model are immediately reflected in what is being observed.

This inherent *reflexivity* of observation made Mead (1968) call for cyberneticians to assume responsibility for the social and ecological consequences of their models. The cybernetic study of control became understood more deeply as a means of exerting control as well, and the formulation of cybernetic descriptions as a means of adding new regulatory circuits of communication. These second-order effects of observation, aphoristically summed up as "the control of control and the communication of communication" (Von Foerster, 1974), are well illustrated in the works of Stafford Beer and Gordon Pask. Beer, in his "Project Cybersyn" implemented in Chile in 1971–1973 during the Allende presidency, designed a complex technological system which redistributed the decision-making power from the state's administration to the industrial workforce, thus enabling self-regulation of the national economy. Pask, in his *Conversation Theory* (1975), developed a cybernetic and dialectic theory of learning, which explained how communication leads to the "construction of knowledge" with the help of a metalanguage that makes the knowledge explicit.

One of the most profound theoretical outcomes of the second-order fascination with the circularity of cognitive operations was the biological theory of living systems developed by Maturana and Varela (2010). Seeking a biological definition of life, Maturana and Varela proposed that a living unit defines and maintains itself by the process of *autopoiesis*: a continuous, recursive self-creation of the system, realised via the production of its own components as attended to by its other components, and guided by cognitive activity. They concluded that "living as a process is a process of cognition". The philosophy that knowledge is the product of an autonomous, self-maintaining system was elaborated in Ernst von Glasersfeld's *radical*

constructivism: a theory of knowledge in which knowledge does not reflect an objective reality and cannot be simply transmitted from one cognitive system to the next, but arises as "exclusively an ordering and organization of a world constituted by the experience" (Glaserfeld, 1984).

Continuations in the social sciences

After the 1st Macy conference a special "subconference" was organised to involve social sciences. The 1946 meeting allowed many social scientists to hear from Wiener and von Neumann. This probably inspired Talcott Parsons and Robert Merton, who both published their systemic and functionalist social theories within the next few years. While Parsons and Merton never joined the Macy group, the prominent social scientist Kurt Lewin was a founding member (he died after the 2nd meeting). Lewin's thinking was particularly influential in the Group Processes Conferences (1954-1960)—a series that directly followed the cybernetics conferences, retaining Mead and Bateson as core members, while focusing on second-order reflexivity in group dynamics.

Niklas Luhmann, in his *social systems* theory (1984) further developed and integrated two central lines of second-order cybernetic thinking: one describing the additional circuits of communication and control introduced by scientific models and one explaining the unity of existence of a cognising system with the processes of its cognition. Both lines illustrated the "observing the observer" character of second-order epistemology, but in a different manner. By applying the concept of autopoiesis to social systems, Luhmann's theory joined them together. For Luhmann, social systems exist by means of an on-going self-observation, which orients the re-production of their components. These components are *communications*, i.e. observations of selections of meaning. A social system then maintains its continued existence through the re-production of instances of communication. The self-reference of the "cybernetics of cybernetics" can be seen as an example of a social system of communication starting to observe this process "from within". Luhmann extended this way of thinking to a general social theory (the "society of society"), which is applicable to any social system and to society at large.

Today, the second-order epistemology and social systems theory continue to be investigated by the *sociocybernetics* group within sociology (Geyer, 1995; Almaguer-Kalixto & Giglietto, 2019), and by its semiotically oriented branch named *cybersemiotics* (Brier, 2008).

The legacy of the field

Despite its important historical role, cybernetics has not become established as an autonomous discipline. There are just a few research departments and education programs devoted to the subject. Part of the problem is the difficulty of maintaining the coherence of a broad, theoretical field in the wake of the popularity of its more specialised applications (Heylighen & Joslyn, 2001). Another is the loss of scientific reputation due to unwarranted over-generalisations and insufficient mutual recognition by the contributing disciplines (Kline, 2015). After the split in 1968, the label "cybernetics" was only rarely used by the scientists identified with the first-order side, which branched into independent disciplines such as Information Theory, Control Theory, and Control Systems Engineering. *Second-order cybernetics* largely gave way to enactive and embodied cognitive science and epistemological constructivism. The scholars most interested in the integrative aspects of cybernetics tended to gravitate towards Systems Science (whose 1950's precursor General Systems Theory had already strongly cross-fertilized with cybernetics), and later Complexity Science. Cybernetics as a theoretical framework remains a subject of study for a few committed groups, such as the American Society for Cybernetics. Scattered research centers, particularly in Central and Eastern Europe, are still devoted to specific technical applications, such as biological cybernetics, medical cybernetics, or engineering cybernetics, although they tend to keep closer contact with their fields of application.

Notwithstanding its lack of institutionalisation, cybernetics has strongly influenced its contributing fields, while playing a seminal role in the birth of numerous new ones, such as Cognitive Science, Computer Science, Information Science, Modelling and Simulation, Artificial Intelligence, Dynamical Systems, Robotics, and Neural Networks. Many of the core ideas of cybernetics, such as complexity, networks, autonomy, adaptation, and self-organisation, continue to influence scientific developments. As reflected by the ubiquitous prefix "cyber-", some of these ideas have pervaded popular culture, albeit in a rather shallow manner. However, other core cybernetic ideas, such as the crucial role of feedback and self-reference, tend to be neglected, while being periodically rediscovered in different domains. Perhaps the most significant

resurgence can be found in the domains of Artificial Life and Complex Adaptive Systems, which model the self-organization of networks of interacting agents. It seems likely that as the interactions between human individuals, communication processes and technological systems become increasingly complex and pervading, the need will again be felt for a conceptual framework that can help us to understand the meaning of these developments, as was the original intent of cybernetics.

SEE ALSO: Autopoiesis, Bateson, Complexity and Emergence, Distinction, Group Processes, Lewin, Luhmann, Operations Management, Mead, System Theories.

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